

Synthesis and characterization of *s*-triazine based 1,5-benzothiazepines and isoxazoles

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Manuscript received 18 August 2009, revised 23 February 2009, accepted 25 February 2010

Abstract : Series of compounds 2,4-bis-phenylamino-6-[4'-(2''-(substituted phenyl/cinnamyl/2'''-furanyl/2'''-thienyl)-2'',3''-dihydro-1'',5''-benzothiazepine-4''-yl)phenyl amino]-*s*-triazine 7(a-f) were prepared by reaction of different chalcones and 2-amino thiophenol in the presence of glacial acetic acid.

Chalcones 6(a-f) on cyclisation with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of alkali gave 2,4-bis-phenylamino-6-[4'-(5''-(substituted phenyl/cinnamyl/2'''-furanyl/2'''-thienyl)-2''-isoxazol-3''-yl)phenyl amino]-*s*-triazine 8(a-f). The products were characterized by elemental analysis, IR and ¹H NMR data. All the synthesized compounds have been evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against four different strain viz. *S. aureus* (MTCC-96), *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441) (Gram-positive bacteria) and *E. coli* (MTCC-443), *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733) (Gram-negative bacteria) by agar diffusion method.

Keywords : Chalcones, benzothiazepines, isoxazoles, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Benzothiazepine is a benzo-annulated example of thiazepine. Thiazepine is a seven membered ring compound containing N and S as hetero atoms. Literature survey reveals that 1,5-benzothiazepines possess wide spectrum of pharmacological activities such as chemotherapeutic¹, CNS depressant², cardiovascular³ and antimicrobial⁴ etc.

Five membered heterocycles like isoxazoles have found wide application as pharmaceutical and agrochemical agents. The synthesis of isoxazole derivatives has attracted considerable attention from organic and medicinal chemists due to their considerable bioactivities. Various biological applications have been reported for isoxazoles such as antiprotozoal⁵, antibacterial⁶ and anticonvulsant⁷. In continuation of our work⁸, we have synthesized some novel benzothiazepines and isoxazoles from chalcones.

Results and discussion

The target molecule were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96), *B. subtilis* (MTCC-

441) [Gram-positive bacteria] and *E. coli* (MTCC-443), *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733) [Gram-negative bacteria] by using agar diffusion method of Barry⁹. Known antibiotic Ciprofloxacin was used as standard drug. Compounds 7(a), 7(b), 7(d), 7(f), 8(d) and 8(f) were found to be less active against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96), whereas compounds 7(c), 7(e), 8(a), 8(c) and 8(e) were found to be inactive against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96). Compounds 7(b), 7(f) and 8(f) were found to be moderately active against *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441), whereas compounds 7(e), 8(a), 8(b), 8(c), 8(d) and 8(e) were found to be less active against *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441). Whereas compound 7(a) was found to be inactive against *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441). Compounds 7(b), 7(d), 8(a), 8(c), 8(d), 8(e) and 8(f) were found to be moderately active against *E. coli* (MTCC-443), whereas compounds 7(a), 7(c), 7(f) and 8(b) were found to be less active against *E. coli* (MTCC-443). Compound 7(e) was found to be inactive against *E. coli* (MTCC-443). Compounds 7(a), 7(c) and 7(e) were found to be moderately active against *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733). Compounds

Scheme

7(b), 8(a), 8(d) and 8(f) were found to be moderately active against *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733). Compounds 7(f), 8(c), 8(b) and 8(e) were found to be less active against *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733).

Table 1. Molecular formula, melting point and yield of compounds 7(a-f) and 8(a-f)

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
7a	4-Fluorophenyl	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ N ₇ SF	84	78
7b	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethyl aminophenyl	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₈ S	90	74
7c	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethyl aminophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₃₈ N ₈ S	110	65
7d	Cinnamyl	C ₃₈ H ₃₁ N ₇ S	96	68
7e	2-Furanyl	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ N ₇ OS	96	66
7f	2-Thienyl	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ N ₇ S ₂	85	70
8a	4-Fluorophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₇ OF	120	74
8b	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethyl aminophenyl	C ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₈ O	166	78
8c	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethyl aminophenyl	C ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₈ O	138	69
8d	Cinnamyl	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₇ O	131	71
8e	2-Furanyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₇ O ₂	110	60
8f	2-Thienyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₇ OS	157	67

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker Avance DPX 400 MHz spectrometer with CDCl₃ as solvent and tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was conducted with Silica Gel 60 F-254 (Merck) plates of 0.25 mm thickness eluted with visualized UV (254 nm) or iodine to check the purity of the synthesized compounds.

Preparation of 2,4-bis-phenylamino-6-[4'-'2''-(substituted phenyl/cinnamyl/2''-furanyl/2''-thienyl)-2'',3''-dihydro-1'',5''-benzothiazepine-4''-yl]phenyl amino]-s-triazine 7(a) : Compound 6(a) (0.01 mol) and 2-amino thiophenol (0.01 mol) in alcohol (30 mL) were refluxed for 12 h in the presence of glacial acetic acid (5 mL). The progress of reaction was monitored on TLC plate. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into crushed ice. The product separated out was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from alcohol to give 7(a). Similarly the compounds 7(b-f) were prepared by this method.

Compound 7(a) : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3025 (=CH str), 1556 (C=C str), 827 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3395

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of the compounds 7(a-f) and 8(a-f)

Compd.	R	Antibacterial activity			
		Diameter of zone of inhibition (in mm)			
		<i>S. aureus</i> MTCC-96	<i>B. subtilis</i> MTCC-441	<i>E. coli</i> MTCC-443	<i>S. paratyphi-B</i> MTCC-733
7a	4-Fluorophenyl	13	-	12	11
7b	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethyl aminophenyl	11	14	17	15
7c	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethyl aminophenyl	-	15	14	22
7d	Cinnamyl	12	17	16	19
7e	2-Furanyl	-	13	-	22
7f	2-Thienyl	10	14	12	12
8a	4-Fluorophenyl	-	13	18	16
8b	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethyl aminophenyl	-	12	10	15
8c	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethyl aminophenyl	-	11	16	14
8d	Cinnamyl	10	11	17	18
8e	2-Furanyl	-	13	18	13
8f	2-Thienyl	11	14	18	15
	Ciprofloxacin (Standard drugs)	22	21	24	25

(N-H str), 1573 (C=N str), 1012 (C-F str), 802 (C-N, *s*-triazine), 731 (C-S-C str); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 3.10 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_a$ benzothiazepine moiety), 3.35 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_b$ benzothiazepine moiety), 5.00 (1H, dd, -CH benzothiazepine moiety), 6.90–8.10 (25H, m, 22 Ar-H and 3 NH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 40.1, 50.1, 111.4 (2), 115.5 (2), 117.0, 117.8 (4), 122.4 (2), 125.8, 127.4, 127.9, 129.3 (2), 129.7 (4), 130.5 (2), 133.4, 137.6, 138.2 (2), 139.1, 141.2, 155.6, 161.3, 162.5, 164.6, 167.3 (2) (Found : C, 70.81; H, 4.12; N, 16.01. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_7\text{SF}$: C, 70.92; H, 4.62; N, 16.08%).

Compound 7(b) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3010 (=CH str), 1546 (C=C str), 810 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3397 (N-H str), 1568 (C=N str), 816 (C-N, *s*-triazine), 722 (C-S-C str); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 3.09 (6H, s, -CH₃), 3.21 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_a$ benzothiazepine moiety), 3.65 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_b$ benzothiazepine moiety), 5.31 (1H, dd, -CH benzothiazepine moiety), 6.90–8.10 (25H, m, 22 Ar-H and 3 NH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 38.1, 41.3 (2), 51.1, 112.5 (2), 112.9 (2), 117.5 (4), 118.1, 123.0 (2), 124.6, 128.2, 128.6 (2), 128.9 (4), 129.9 (2), 133.0, 134.2, 136.5, 137.8 (2), 140.8, 149.0, 154.8, 161.9, 168.5 (2), 226.6 (2) (Found : C, 71.21; H, 5.19; N, 17.01. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_8\text{S}$: C, 71.90; H, 5.39; N, 17.65%).

Compound 7(c) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3055 (=CH str), 1580 (C=C str), 805 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3357 (N-H str), 1549 (C=N str), 840 (C-N, *s*-triazine), 780 (C-S-C str); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 1.20 (6H, t, -CH₃), 3.42 (4H, m, -CH₂), 3.21 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_a$ benzothiazepine moiety), 3.65 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_b$ benzothiazepine moiety), 5.31 (1H, dd, -CH benzothiazepine moiety), 6.90–8.10 (25H, m, 22 Ar-H and 3 NH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 12.9 (2), 39.4, 47.1 (2), 55.1, 112.4 (2), 112.9 (2), 117.8 (4), 118.6, 123.3 (2), 124.9, 128.2, 128.6 (2), 128.9 (4), 129.9 (2), 132.8, 134.2, 136.9, 137.8 (2), 140.8, 149.0, 155.8, 161.9, 168.5 (2), 226.6 (2) (Found : C, 71.81; H, 5.17; N, 16.21. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_8\text{S}$: C, 72.48; H, 5.77; N, 16.91%).

Compound 7(d) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3110 (=CH str), 1565 (C=C str), 800 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3387 (N-H str), 1594 (C=N str), 848 (C-N, *s*-triazine), 750 (C-S-C str); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 3.21 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_a$ benzothiazepine moiety), 3.65 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_b$ benzothiazepine moiety), 5.31 (1H, dd, -CH benzothiazepine moiety), 6.90–8.10 (26H, m, 23 Ar-H and 3 NH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 39.4, 55.1, 112.4 (2), 117.8 (4), 118.6, 123.3 (2), 124.9, 126.3, 127.9, 128.5 (4), 128.2, 128.9 (4), 129.9 (2), 130.0, 134.2, 136.4, 136.9, 137.8

(2), 140.8, 155.8, 161.9, 168.5 (2), 226.6 (2) (Found : C, 72.77; H, 5.04; N, 15.85. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_7\text{S}$: C, 72.88; H, 5.05; N, 15.87%).

Compound 7(e) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3115 (=CH str), 1565 (C=C str), 803 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3394 (N-H str), 1590 (C=N str), 850 (C-N, *s*-triazine), 755 (C-S-C str); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 3.21 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_a$ benzothiazepine moiety), 3.65 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_b$ benzothiazepine moiety), 5.31 (1H, dd, -CH benzothiazepine moiety), 6.90–8.10 (24H, m, 21 Ar-H and 3 NH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 39.4, 55.1, 107.2, 110.0, 112.4 (2), 117.8 (4), 118.6, 123.3 (2), 124.9, 128.9 (4), 129.9 (2), 134.2, 136.9, 137.8 (2), 140.8, 141.5, 154.3, 155.8, 161.9, 168.5 (2), 226.6 (2) (Found : C, 70.09; H, 4.60; N, 16.80. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_7\text{OS}$: C, 70.21; H, 4.67; N, 16.86%).

Compound 7(f) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3110 (=CH str), 1560 (C=C str), 801 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3390 (N-H str), 1595 (C=N str), 855 (C-N, *s*-triazine), 760 (C-S-C str); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 3.21 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_a$ benzothiazepine moiety), 3.65 (2H, dd, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}_b$ benzothiazepine moiety), 5.31 (1H, dd, -CH benzothiazepine moiety), 6.90–8.10 (24H, m, 21 Ar-H and 3 NH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 39.4, 55.1, 112.4 (2), 117.8 (4), 118.6, 123.3 (2), 124.9, 125.5, 126.7, 127.0, 128.9 (4), 129.9 (2), 134.2, 136.9, 137.8 (2), 140.8, 147.2, 155.8, 161.9, 168.5 (2), 226.6 (2) (Found : C, 68.30; H, 4.55; N, 16.35. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_7\text{S}_2$: C, 68.32; H, 4.55; N, 16.40%).

Preparation of 2,4-bis-phenylamino-6-{4'-(5''-(substituted phenyl/cinnamyl)/2''-furanlyl/2''-thienyl)-2''-isoxazol-3''-yl}phenyl amino]-s-triazine 8(a) : Compound 6(a) (0.01 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 6 h in the presence of 2 mL of 40% KOH solution in ethanol (30 mL). The progress of reaction was monitored on TLC plate. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice and neutralized with dilute HCl. The product separated out was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from alcohol to give 8(a). Similarly the compounds 8(b-f) were prepared by this method.

Compound 8(a) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3030 (=CH str), 1550 (C=C str), 837 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3380 (N-H str), 1583 (C=N str, isoxazole moiety), 1012 (C-F str), 808 (C-N, *s*-triazine); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 6.98 (1H, s, -CH, isoxazole moiety), 6.90–7.80 (21H, m, 18 Ar-H and 3 NH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 98.3, 116.0 (2),

116.8 (2), 117.8 (4), 118.2, 122.2, 122.4 (2), 127.2 (2), 128.3 (2), 129.5 (4), 138.9 (2), 139.0, 162.0 (2), 162.5, 162.9, 167.3 (2), 169.3 (Found : C, 69.30; H, 4.10; N, 19.00. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{22}N_7OF$: C, 69.89; H, 4.30; N, 19.02%).

Compound **8(b)** : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3035 (=CH str), 1540 (C=C str), 858 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3387 (N-H str), 1573 (C=N str, isoxazole moiety), 818 (C-N, *s*-triazine); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 3.09 (6H, s, -CH₃), 6.98 (1H, s, -CH, isoxazole moiety), 6.90-7.80 (21H, m, 18 Ar-H and 3 NH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 41.3 (2), 98.3, 111.7 (2), 116.8 (2), 117.8 (4), 118.2, 122.4 (2), 128.3 (2), 129.5 (4), 129.8 (2), 131.6, 138.9 (2), 139.0, 162.0 (2), 162.5, 167.3 (2), 169.3 (Found : C, 71.05; H, 5.10; N, 19.00. Calcd. for $C_{32}H_{28}N_8O$: C, 71.10; H, 5.22; N, 19.02%).

Compound **8(c)** : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3085 (=CH str), 1540 (C=C str), 850 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3380 (N-H str), 1543 (C=N str, isoxazole moiety), 800 (C-N, *s*-triazine); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 1.25 (6H, t, -CH₃), 3.62 (4H, m, -CH₂), 6.90 (1H, s, -CH, isoxazole moiety), 6.90-7.80 (21H, m, 18 Ar-H and 3 NH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 12.9 (2), 47.1 (2), 98.3, 112.7 (2), 116.8 (2), 117.8 (4), 118.2, 122.4 (2), 128.3 (2), 129.1 (2), 129.5 (4), 132.2, 138.9 (2), 139.0, 162.0 (2), 162.5, 167.3 (2), 169.3 (Found : C, 71.15; H, 5.19; N, 19.70. Calcd. for $C_{34}H_{32}N_8O$: C, 71.81; H, 5.67; N, 19.71%).

Compound **8(d)** : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3030 (=CH str), 1540 (C=C str), 830 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3380 (N-H str), 1573 (C=N str, isoxazole moiety), 808 (C-N, *s*-triazine); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 6.98 (1H, s, -CH, isoxazole moiety), 6.90-7.80 (21H, m, 18 Ar-H and 3 NH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 98.3, 116.8 (2), 117.8 (4), 118.2, 122.4 (2), 127.9, 128.3 (2), 128.5 (4), 129.5 (4), 134.5, 137.7, 138.9 (2), 139.0, 162.0 (2), 162.5, 167.3 (2), 169.3 (Found : C, 73.30; H, 4.60; N, 18.70. Calcd. for $C_{32}H_{25}N_7O$: C, 73.41; H, 4.81; N, 18.73%).

Compound **8(e)** : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3084 (=CH str), 1542 (C=C str), 850 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3381 (N-H str), 1545 (C=N str, isoxazole moiety), 800 (C-N, *s*-triazine); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 6.90 (1H, s, -CH, isoxazole moiety), 6.90-7.80 (20H, m, 17 Ar-H and 3 NH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 98.3, 112.7, 116.8 (2), 117.8 (4),

118.2, 122.4 (2), 128.3 (2), 129.5 (4), 138.9 (2), 139.0, 143.7, 146.6, 162.0 (2), 162.5, 167.3 (2), 169.3 (Found : C, 68.80; H, 4.30; N, 20.08. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{21}N_7O_2$: C, 68.99; H, 4.34; N, 20.11%).

Compound **8(f)** : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3074 (=CH str), 1540 (C=C str), 853 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 3380 (N-H str), 1545 (C=N str, isoxazole moiety), 808 (C-N, *s*-triazine); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 6.90 (1H, s, -CH, isoxazole moiety), 6.90-7.80 (20H, m, 17 Ar-H and 3 NH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 98.3, 116.8 (2), 117.1, 117.8 (4), 122.4 (2), 128.3 (2), 128.8, 129.5 (4), 130.5, 136.6, 138.9 (2), 139.0, 162.0 (2), 162.5, 167.3 (2), 169.3 (Found : C, 66.70; H, 4.10; N, 19.44. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{21}N_7OS$: C, 66.78; H, 4.20; N, 19.47%).

Acknowledgement

Author is grateful to B. K. M. Science College, Valsad for providing research facilities and to Microbiology Department for carrying out antibacterial activity. Atul Ltd. (Atul) for the IR spectral analysis and G.V.K. Bioscience Pvt. Ltd. (Hyderabad) for the 1H NMR spectral analysis.

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